

Advanced In Biomass And Biogas Energy

Abdeen Mustafa Omer*

Energy Research Institute, Forest Road West, Nottingham, UK

Email: abdeenomer2@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract:

There is strong scientific evidence that the average temperature of the earth's surface is rising and this may be attribute to increased concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂), and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere as released by burning fossil fuels. One of the chief sources of greenhouse gases is burning of fossil fuels. Biogas from biomass appears to have potential as an alternative energy source, which is potentially rich in biomass resources. In the present study, current literature is reviewed regarding the ecological, social, cultural and economic impacts of biogas technology. In this communication an attempt has been made to give an overview of present and future use of biomass as an industrial feedstock for production of fuels, chemicals and other materials. However, to be truly competitive in an open market situation, higher value products are required.

Keywords:

Biomass resources; biogas application; sustainable development; environment

Studies towards the total synthesis of Linotrins and its evaluation against bacterial infections leading to Stroke

Sujit Dey¹, Thierry Durand*,¹ Nicolas Blondeau², Laurence Balas¹

¹ Institut des Biomolécules Max Mousseron (IBMM), UMR 5247, Université de Montpellier, CNRS, ENSCM, 34093 Montpellier Cedex 5, France

² Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, IPMC, UMR7275 Sophia Antipolis, F-06560, France.

Email: iictsujit@gmail.com

Abstract:

Infections and stroke are linked through inflammation. Common viral and bacterial infections can increase the susceptibility to stroke by promoting inflammation, thrombosis and atherosclerosis. 1 Reciprocally, stroke commonly leads to disruption of protective mechanisms against infection and induces a cascade of anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive reactions, which greatly increases the risk of infection that, in turn, complicated acute stroke in 30% of patients.

2. Recent investigation suggested a potential role of lipoxygenase derived lipid mediators in infectious diseases. 3 Protectin DX (PDX), an omega-3 lipid metabolite derived from docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) has beneficial effects in infectious diseases: for instance, inhibition 4-5 of influenza virus replication; increased survival in mouse model of sepsis 6. In addition, α -linolenic acid (ALA) supplementation prevented mortality and cerebral damage in model of ischemic stroke. 7 Its lipoxygenase metabolites, called linotrins, which possess a similar E,Z,E conjugated triene as PDX, may produce immunomodulation and reduced bacterial infections that are risk factors of stroke. Thus, the our project aims at evaluating the bioactivities of linotrins against bacterial infections and against brain inflammation. We have successfully validated a 15 step strategy yielding linotrin in milligram scale. The chemical synthesis features highly stereoselective hydrometalation reactions to build the three desired double bonds. A Suzuki cross-coupling reaction afforded the expected conjugated E,Z,E-triene from Pre cursors A and B with excellent retention of the stereochemistry. Preliminary biological experiments were performed in microglial cells using bacterial endotoxin lipopolysaccharide (LPS) as pro-inflammatory stimulus. Linotrin induced significant reduction of interleukins IL-1 β and IL-6, and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α). Interestingly, it reduced inflammation at lower concentration than ALA. Further in vitro investigation including evaluation of its protective effects on different cytokines and chemokines (especially on subsequent release of CCL2, known to be triggered by LPS) and LPS-challenged HT22 neuronal cells lines and/or cortical neuronal cells are under investigation.

Keywords:

Inflammation, infectious disease, Lipids, medicinal chemistry, Total Synthesis.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the synthrtic scheme for the total synthesis of linotrin.

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Heterotrimeric complex of p38 MAPK, PKC δ , and TIRAP is required for AP1 mediated inflammatory response.

Baig M S

Centre for Biosciences and Biomedical Engineering (BSBE), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), India

Abstract:

Inflammation could be described as a physiological response of the body to tissue injury, pathogen invasion, and irritants. During the inflammatory phase, cells of both the innate as well as adaptive immune system are activated and recruited to the site of inflammation. These mediators are downstream targets for the transcription factors; activator protein-1 (AP1), nuclear factor kappa light chain enhancer (NF- κ B), signal transducers and activators of transcription factors (STAT1), as well as interferon regulatory factors (IRFs), which control the expression of most immunomodulatory genes. There is a significant increase in active p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (p38MAPK) immediately after lipopolysaccharide (LPS) stimulation, which results in the activation of AP-1 transcription factor and expression of proinflammatory cytokines, IL-12 and IL-23. We studied the novel mechanism of p38 MAPK activation through the formation of a heterotrimeric complex of Protein kinase C delta type (PKC δ), Toll-Interleukin 1 Receptor (TIR) Domain Containing Adaptor Protein (TIRAP), and p38 proteins. TIRAP serves as an adaptor molecule which brings PKC δ and p38 in close proximity. The complex facilitates the activation of p38MAPK by PKC δ . Therefore, we propose that disruption of the heterotrimeric complex may be a good strategy to dampen the inflammatory response.

Keywords:

Inflammation, heterotrimeric complex, AP1, NF- κ B, STAT1, LPS

Figure 1: Heterotrimer complex of PKC δ -TIRAP-p38 mediated inflammatory response in macrophages. (1) LPS from Gram-negative bacteria stimulates TLR4 receptor in macrophages; (2) This induces the activation of the AP1 signaling pathway via heterotrimer complex of PKC δ -TIRAP-p38; (3) LPS stimulation activates PKC δ , which in result phosphorylates p38 MAPK (4, 5) p38 MAPK activation induces AP1 transcriptional activity and expression of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-12, IL-23.

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Secondary metabolites from medicinally important weed: *Achyranthes aspera*

Rashmi^a and Akito Nagatsu^b

Department of Basic Science, Sardar Vallab Bhai Patel University of Agriculture & Technology, Meerut, India.

Email: sehrawat82@gmail.com

Abstract:

Achyranthes Linn (Family: Amaranthaceae), a genus of stiff herbs, is distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical regions. *Achyranthes aspera*, an erect annual herb (0.3-0.9m in height) is distributed throughout India (upto1000m), Baluchistan, Ceylon, Tropical Asia, Africa, Australia and America. The plant possesses diuretic, purgative properties and act as an antidote against snakebite. Seeds are emetic and used against renal dropsy and hydrophobia. The plant extract is also used as abortifacient and contraceptive. Presence of ecdysterone in its roots causes insect molting activity. Literature survey revealed that triterpene glycosides, aliphatic compounds, steroids, fatty acids, alkaloids and betaine have been characterized from its different parts.

The present investigation describes the isolation of three oleanolic acid glycosides from the seeds of and four steroidal triterpenes from the leaves, stem and roots of *Achyranthes aspera* collected from Dehra Dun. The structures of these compounds were elucidated as 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)-Oleanolic acid [A], 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)-Oleanolic acid-28-O-- β -D-glucopyranoside[B], 3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-(glucopyranosyl uronic acid)- Oleanolic acid-28-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside [C], Spinasterol [D], Stigmasterol [E], α -spinasterol acetate [F] on the basis of 1H NMR, 13C NMR, 2D NMR, MS spectral data and β -sitosterol [G] by direct comparison with an authentic sample. The compounds A, C, D and E are reported for the first time in *Achyranthes* genus. The occurrence of compound A and C is being reported first time. Antioxidant potential of the isolated compounds was also assessed by different bioassays. The results will be discussed in detail during presentation.

Key words:

Secondary metabolites, *Achyranthes aspera*, amaranthaceae, triterpenoids

Stimulated production of oxidatively-truncated phospholipids defines a new pathway of cytokine-induced cell death

Latchoumycandane Calivarathan^{1,2} and Thomas M. McIntyre¹

¹Department of Cellular and Molecular Medicine, Lerner Research Institute, USA

²Department of Life Sciences, School of Life Sciences, Central University of Tamil Nadu, India

Email: latchoumycandane@cutn.ac.in

Abstract:

TNF- α is an inflammatory cytokine, known to modulate cell survival and proliferation by the activation of NF- κ B-dependent pathway where simultaneous activation of caspase regulates apoptosis. TNF α generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) required in cell death, but their molecular identity and mode of action remain undefined. We demonstrate that oxidatively truncated phospholipids connect TNF α to apoptosis. In the present study we showed that TNF- α stimulated ROS production by Nox4 in Jurkat cells that oxidized cellular polyunsaturated phospholipids. Glutathione peroxidase-4 (GPx4), which uniquely metabolizes these to non-reactive lipid alcohols, fell in TNF- α stimulated cells prior to death. Overexpression of GPx4 ameliorated, while GPx4 siRNA knockdown enhanced, apoptosis. Phospholipid hydroperoxides are unstable with fragmentation of the esterified oxidized fatty acyl chain, forming truncated phospholipids. The truncated product azelaoyl phosphatidylcholine (Az-PC)—a mitotoxic and pro-apoptotic phospholipid—accumulated after TNF α stimulation. Over-expression of GPx4 or PAFAH2 that specifically hydrolyzes oxidized phospholipids suppressed Az-PC accumulation, and each enzyme prevented TNF- α stimulated cell death. Accordingly, exogenous Az-PC bypassed the protection afforded by GPx4 over-expression. Truncated phospholipids are common effectors of stimulated apoptosis required for TNF- α cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells, and FasL induced death of Jurkat cells. Thus, cytokines stimulate ROS production that oxidizes cellular polyunsaturated phospholipids, which then fragment to mitotoxic truncated phospholipids that are required components of stimulated apoptosis.

Assessment Of Heavy Metals In Water, Fish And Sediments In Dams Around Mining Vicinities In Zamfara State, Nigeria.

¹ Moses Sunday, ² Wyasu, Gideon

¹ Department of Chemistry, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

² Department of Chemistry, Kaduna state University, Kaduna, Nigeria

Email: akamomoses@yahoo.com

Abstract:

The concentrations of heavy metals in water, sediment and fish (*Tillapia Monsambicus*) in the three major dams in Zamfara State along gold mining vicinities were determined using standard methods for two years in 2014 and 2015 (four seasons). The concentration of heavy metals determined in water, sediment, and fish were generally high during the dry season with exception of Hg which recorded its highest concentration in year 2015. Zn and Cr levels in the water, sediment, and fish were within international safe limits while Cd (0.1022 mg/l), Pb (0.2104 mg/l) and Hg (1.8818 mg/l) levels were far above (0.01, 0.01 and 0.001mg/l) USEPA safe limits respectively for drinking water. Two major indices such as contamination factor (CF) and pollution load index (PLI) were used for determining the contamination level of water, sediment, and fish samples. The result revealed a high contamination factor for Cd, Pb and Hg across all the six locations and a general overall pollution load across all the locations. Generally, the concentration of the analyzed heavy metals in mg/l for water and sediments was in the order of Hg > Pb > Cd > Cr > Zn. Correlation analysis showed a significant and positive relationship for Cd and Zn and Hg and Cr during the wet season and a significant positive at the ($p > 0.05$) relationship for Cr and Zn in the dry season. The pollution index value of the water samples across all the three dams indicated that there is need for immediate intervention to ameliorate pollution particularly in the dry season.

Keywords:

Dams, Heavy metals, sediments, fish and gold mining.

Synthesis Of Azomethines Of Anthrones And 10- Arylidene Anthrones And Testing For Anticancer And Antiaids Activity.

Dr. Mahesh N. Sanzgiri

Nadkarni- Sacasa research laboratory, St. Xavier's college, India

Abstract:

A new series of azomethines of anthrones have been prepared by condensing anthrone with different primary amines, o-aminophenol and p-aminobenzoic acid.

Similarly 10-Arylidene anthrones with different functional groups were synthesized using Acetic Anhydrite as well as ethanol as solvent.

It is found that Azomethines of anthrones prepared by condensing primary amines with nitro group in p-position of aromatic ring indicate intense anticancer activity *in situ* as compared to other azomethines of anthrones. It is also proved that azomethine group stabilized by aromatic ring shows anti-cancer activity, but Nitro group in p-position of aromatic ring can be considered for further investigation for development of anticancer drug, after doing detailed toxicity studies. Similarly 10-Arylidene anthrones with Nitro group in p-position of aromatic ring shows anti-aids activity *in situ*. However detailed studies of toxicity should be done before considering for further development of anti-aids drugs.

This study also includes structure activity relationship and new reaction mechanism which involves bending of functional group.

Keywords:

Azomethines, 10-Arylidene, structure activity, reaction mechanism.

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Overcoming the Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) with peptide-conjugates

M. Cavaco^{1,2}, D. Gaspar¹, S. Frutos³, M. Vila-Perello³, D. Andreu², M. Castanho¹, V. Neves¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Av Prof Ega, Portugal

² Proteomics and Protein Chemistry Unit, Department of Experimental and Health Sciences, Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona, Biomedical Research Park, Spain

³ ProteoDesign S.L., B, Spain

Abstract:

The blood-brain barrier (BBB) restricts the delivery of therapeutic proteins into the brain. To increase their brain accumulation, therapeutic proteins have been conjugated to trans-BBB peptides. Most trans-BBB peptides target natural receptors on the surface of BBB cells, leading to receptor saturation or competition with natural ligands. The outcome might be the hamper of brain homeostasis. Therefore, we intended to take advantage of the adsorptive-mediated transport to get access into the brain. We have previously reported on the PepH3 peptide that is able to cross the BBB *in vitro* and *in vivo* un-conjugated and conjugated to GFP or antibody fragments. In this work, we have evaluated *in vitro* the capacity of PepH3 to increase the BBB translocation of an Fc domain of an IgG. To do so, we chemically conjugated PepH3 to the Fc domain via streamlined expressed protein ligation (SEPL) (Figure 1 A) to obtain a chemically well-defined Fc-PepH3 conjugate (Figure 1 B). While the Fc alone does not translocate the *in vitro* BBB model, the conjugation to PepH3 results in a translocation comparable to the well-established Fc5 single antibody.

Keywords:

Trans-BBB peptides, peptide-conjugates, PepH3, adsorptive-mediated transport, blood-brain barrier, therapeutic proteins, translocation, antibodies

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the strategy developed to conjugate PepH3 to the Fc domain of an IgG. A) Scheme of the Streamlined Ex-pressed Protein Ligation (SEPL) applied in the conjugation. B) The final product obtained after the SEPL reaction with two PepH3 conjugated to the Fc domain.

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